

FINANCIAL RISKS CHINESE MANUFACTURING FIRMS FACE AND SUGGESTED INTERNATIONAL PRACTICES FROM ADVANCED ECONOMIES

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Abstract. This study examines international financial risk management (FRM) practices and compares them with the financial situation of Chinese manufacturing firms to identify lessons for emerging markets. Firms in advanced economies widely apply structured FRM systems, including hedging, balanced capital structures, strong liquidity management, and comprehensive risk governance. In contrast, Chinese manufacturing firms face high leverage, heavy reliance on short-term debt, weak liquidity, low profitability, and underdeveloped internal controls. Emerging-market enterprises could significantly improve resilience by adopting global FRM tools, strengthening governance structures and improving financial flexibility. The findings offer implications for policymakers and managers seeking to enhance FRM in the real sector.

Key words: financial risk management, international practices, Chinese manufacturing enterprises, hedging, balanced capital structures.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot xalqaro moliyaviy risklarni boshqarish (MRB) amaliyotlarini o'rganadi, hamda ularni Xitoyning ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalari moliyaviy holati bilan taqqoslab, rivojlanayotgan bozorlar uchun foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan xulosalarni aniqlaydi. Rivojlangan iqtisodiyotlarda faoliyat yurituvchi korxonalar hedjlash, muvozanatli kapital tuzilmasi, kuchli likvidlik boshqaruvi va kompleks risklarni boshqarish mexanizmlarini o'z ichiga olgan tizimli MRB usullarini keng qo'llaydi. Aksincha, Xitoy ishlab chiqarish korxonalari yuqori qarzdorlik darajasi, qisqa muddatli qarzga yuqori darajada tayanish, past likvidlik, past rentabellik hamda ichki nazorat tizimlarining yetarlicha rivojlanmaganligi kabi muammolarga duch kelmoqda. Rivojlanayotgan bozor korxonalari global MRB vositalarini qo'llash, korporativ boshqaruvni kuchaytirish va moliyaviy moslashuvchanlikni oshirish orqali barqarorlikni sezilarli darajada yaxshilashi mumkin. Tadqiqot natijalari real sektor korxonalarida MRB tizimlarini takomillashtirishga intilayotganlar va menejerlar uchun amaliy tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: moliyaviy risklarni boshqarish, xalqaro amaliyot, Xitoy ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalari, hedjirlash, muvozanatli kapital tuzilmasi.

Аннотация. В настоящем исследовании рассматриваются международные практики управления финансовыми рисками и проводится их сопоставление с финансовым состоянием китайских производственных предприятий с целью выявления уроков для стран с развивающейся экономикой. Предприятия в развитых странах широко применяют структурированные системы управления финансовыми рисками, включающие хеджирование, сбалансированные структуры капитала, эффективное управление ликвидностью и комплексное управление рисками. В то же время китайские производственные предприятия сталкиваются с высокой долговой нагрузкой, значительной зависимостью от краткосрочного долга, слабой

ликвидностью, низкой прибыльностью и недостаточно развитой системой внутреннего контроля. Предприятия развивающихся стран могут значительно повысить устойчивость, внедряя международные инструменты управления финансовыми рисками, укрепляя корпоративное управление и улучшая финансовую гибкость. Полученные результаты имеют практическое значение для политиков и менеджеров, стремящихся к совершенствованию управления финансовыми рисками в реальном секторе.

Ключевые слова: управление финансовыми рисками, международные практики, китайские производственные предприятия, хеджирование, сбалансированные структуры капитала.

Introduction. Real sector enterprises such as manufacturing, construction, transportation, mining and energy companies, form the backbone of national economies and provide employment, industrial capacity and value-added production. As they operate in an environment where financial markets, global commodity prices, supply chains and currency systems are deeply interconnected, real sector firms face a broad range of financial risks arising from both domestic and international economic conditions. These include interest rate fluctuations, exchange rate volatility, liquidity challenges, increasing levels of debt, price instability of raw materials and intermediate goods. Therefore, it is essential to manage these risks effectively to maintain stability, support long-term investment and sustain competitiveness in the global market. Due to globalization, real sector economy is engaging in cross-border trades, depend on imported raw materials, operate in foreign markets, and often rely on international funding. Despite the offered opportunities, companies are exposed to external shocks such as global demand changes, oil and commodity market fluctuations, currency devaluations. Firms in advanced economies have developed structured and proactive approaches to manage their financial risks such as hedging instruments, balanced capital structures, internal control systems, liquidity planning, and early warning mechanisms for financial distress. In contrast, firms in developing and emerging economies frequently face financial struggles, limited risk management tools, and weaker institutional environments that could intensify their exposure to financial instability. Subsequently, financial risk management (FRM) has become an essential strategic function for worldwide real sector enterprises. To illustrate, China, the world's largest manufacturing base, is a relevant example to understand financial risk management challenges and practices in the real sector. It is apparent that its industrial enterprises are highly sensitive to global market changes, exchange rate fluctuations and international competition. Chinese manufacturing companies tackle serious financial risks related to high debt ratios, liquidity shortages, weak profitability and insufficient internal control mechanisms. Firms' ability to manage financial pressures effectively is limited by these issues and it highlights their need for stronger financial strategies, better early-warning systems, and more robust risk identification practices. Based on these dynamics, learning international practices in financial risk management and using China as a comparative example, gives valuable insights for policymakers, managers, and researchers. China's experience reflects many of the financial vulnerabilities observed in other emerging markets. Thus, it makes it a useful case for understanding how global best practices could be adapted to strengthen enterprises in the real sector economy.

Therefore, the purpose of this article is to examine key international approaches to financial risk management, review the challenges faced by Chinese manufacturing firms and also explore valuable lessons that might be applicable for other developing and emerging economies.

Literature Review. Throughout the recent decades, financial risk management in real sector enterprises has been widely explored across global research. This section will review the primary types of financial risks that manufacturing and service companies face, summarize international practices they use to manage these risks, and provide findings from the Chinese manufacturing sector as a representative example from an emerging economy. Real sector firms face a variety of financial risks due to their operations, financing needs and exposure to markets around the world. The most commonly

identifies risk types include financing risk, liquidity risk, investment risk, credit risk, exchange rate risk, and interest rate risk. All of them directly affect company’s financial performance and long-term sustainability. It should be noted that these risks are especially significant for manufacturing firms that operate with high leverage and depend on global supply chains [1]. Across the world, manufacturing and service firms, especially in the developed economies, apply structured financial risk management techniques to reduce their exposure. The stated methods generally fall into four main categories that are hedging strategies, capital structure management, liquidity planning and internal control systems.

In the global financial risk management hedging strategies are among the most widely used tools. Firms use financial derivatives such as forwards, futures, options and swaps in order to hedge against foreign exchange, commodity, or interest rate risks [2]. To illustrate, exporting firms often secure forward contracts to lock in exchange rates and avoid losses caused by currency fluctuations. Manufacture companies widely use hedging for fuel, metal and agricultural commodity prices to stabilize production costs. Another essential practice is **capital structure management**. International firms frequently aim for a balanced distribution of long-term and short-term funding to eliminate refinancing risk. Companies could protect themselves from sudden interest rate increases or tightening credit markets by relying more on long-term debt. Multinational firms carefully plan their liquidity by substantial cash reserves, establish credit lines with banks, and regularly forecast cash flows to avoid liquidity shortages. Effective liquidity management ensures that firms’ operations remain stable even during periods of revenue volatility [3]. These international practices provide stability and resilience, reducing the likelihood of financial distress while allowing firms to respond effectively to changing market conditions. Research on Chinese listed manufacturing companies reveals multiple financial challenges and weaknesses in risk management practices. According to Fang, many Chinese manufacturing firms illustrate high debt ratios, often rely too heavily on short-term borrowing, which increases refinancing risk. The study also mentions weak liquidity that is caused by limited cash reserves and inefficient working capital management. Additionally, it is difficult for these firms to cover rising financing costs as they frequently suffer from low profitability. The study also highlights problems in the debt structure, where excessive short-term liabilities strain cash flows and lead to unstable financial conditions. Manufacturers in China frequently lack strong internal control mechanisms, including early-warning systems that could detect financial risks before they escalate. Chinese firms are more vulnerable to external shocks such as exchange rate movements, changing global demand and rising commodity prices because of this misalignment between rapid industrial growth and underdeveloped financial risk management systems [4]. These findings reflect challenges and struggles commonly found across emerging markets, where rapid industrial expansion is not always matched by improvements in financial governance, risk identification, and formalized financial risk management practices. Thus, China’s experience provides important insights for other countries seeking to strengthen financial risk management in their own real sector enterprises.

Methodology. The research is based entirely on secondary data, including academic literature and the empirical analysis of Chinese listed manufacturing companies by Fang. A simple comparative framework is used to highlight similarities and differences between global FRM practices and challenges in China.

Discussion. To support the analysis, a summary table was developed that lists the main types of financial risks, their commonly used international management techniques and the specific weaknesses observed in Chinese manufacturing companies.

Table 1. Comparison of Financial Risks, Global Practices, and Chinese Challenges

Financial Risk Area	Global Best Practices	Challenges in Chinese Firms
FX Risk	Hedging with forwards, swaps	High export exposure; limited hedging
Liquidity	Cash buffers; credit lines	Weak liquidity; cash flow shortages

Debt Structure	Balanced long/short-term	Excessive short-term debt
Internal Control	Risk committees; audits	Weak controls; no early-warning systems
Investment Risk	Project evaluation tools	Inefficient investment decisions

The comparison between international financial risk management practices and the financial situation of Chinese manufacturing firms highlights clear differences in financial structure, governance, and resilience. Enterprises in developed economies generally operate with mature FRM systems that integrate financial instruments, liquidity planning, and internal controls. These systems enable firms to control uncertainty related to exchange rates, interest rates, global demand, and input prices more effectively. Hedging is a primary element of international practice. Firms in the USA, Europe, and Japan regularly employ forwards, futures, options, and swaps to reduce exposure to currency, commodity and interest rate risks [2]. This stabilizes revenues and production costs during volatile market conditions. Global firms also maintain more balanced capital structures, relying on higher proportions of long-term financing, which reduces refinancing pressure and vulnerability to rising interest rates. Cash reserves, credit lines, and cash-flow forecasting act as strong liquidity management and support operational continuity during financial shocks [3]. Another governing strength of international firms is risk governance. Many enterprises employ scenario analysis and stress testing to prepare for extreme market conditions. Exporters hedge foreign currency revenue to stabilize income, while manufacturers hedge fuel and metal prices to control production costs. Such measures help maintain financial stability during global market shocks.

In contrast, Chinese manufacturing companies show several structural weaknesses that heighten financial vulnerability. Fang also notes that many listed manufacturers carry high leverage, with a large share of short-term debt, creating significant refinancing pressure. Liquidity management is often weak: firms hold insufficient cash reserves and face inefficient working-capital cycles, limiting their ability to absorb shocks. Low profitability—driven by rising costs and narrow margins—further reduces financial flexibility and increases dependence on debt. Internal control systems are also underdeveloped, as many firms lack risk committees, internal audits, or effective early-warning tools, delaying responses to emerging risks. Combined with exposure to global demand fluctuations and exchange rate movements, these weaknesses amplify overall financial risk. The comparison suggests several lessons for emerging market firms. First, wider adoption of hedging tools is essential to manage currency and commodity risk. Second, improving debt structure by expanding access to long-term financing can enhance financial stability. Third, better liquidity management—including cash reserves and diversified financing sources—can help firms withstand external shocks. Fourth, strengthening internal control and risk governance mechanisms is crucial. Overall, while firms in advanced economies benefit from strong FRM systems, many emerging-market companies—including those in China—still face structural financial weaknesses. Addressing these gaps can significantly improve the resilience and long-term sustainability of real sector enterprises.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the study illustrates that international best practices in financial risk management provide valuable direction for improving the financial stability of firms in emerging markets. While firms in advanced economies benefit from mature FRM systems such as hedging strategies, strong liquidity planning, balanced financing structures and effective governance, many Chinese real sector firms continue to face structural weaknesses that intensifies their exposure to financial shocks. High short-term debt reliance, insufficient liquidity, low profitability and weak internal controls all contribute to increased risk. The comparison suggests several key directions for reform: expanding the use of hedging instruments, increasing access to long-term financing, improving liquidity management, and strengthening internal governance mechanisms. Overall, improving FRM practices is significant for increasing the resilience, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability of real sector enterprises in developing economies.

References

1. **Hull, J. C. (2018).** *Risk Management and Financial Institutions* (5th ed.). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
2. Stulz, R.M. (2003). *Risk Management and Derivatives*. Southwestern College Publishing, Cincinnati. *Scientific Research Publishing*. [online] Available at: <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2053578>.
3. Jorion, P. (2007). *Value at Risk The New Benchmark for Managing Financial Risk. Vol. 3*, McGraw-Hill, New York. *Scientific Research Publishing*. [online] Available at: <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2056015>
4. Fang, F. (2016). A Study of Financial Risks of Listed Manufacturing Companies in China. *Journal of Financial Risk Management*, [online] 5(4), pp.229–245. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4236/jfrm.2016.54022>